

**Large negative magnetoresistance and thermal properties of $\text{Ni}_{50-x}\text{Mn}_{37+x}\text{Sn}_{13}$ ($x = 0, 1, 2, 3$)
Heusler alloys**

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Electrical resistivity and magnetoresistance for $\text{Ni}_{50-x}\text{Mn}_{37+x}\text{Sn}_{13}$ ($x = 0, 1, 2, 3$) have been investigated. In $\text{Ni}_{47}\text{Mn}_{40}\text{Sn}_{13}$, a negative magnetoresistance of 56 % is attained at a field strength of 5T. The drastic change in resistivity upon martensitic transformation is observed for all alloys. The magnetoresistance increases with Mn concentration. The increase in magnetoresistance is ascribed by the super zone boundary gaps. We also investigated thermopower S and thermal conductivity κ for $\text{Ni}_{50-x}\text{Mn}_{37+x}\text{Sn}_{13}$ ($x = 0, 3$) alloys in order to further characterize the heat transport. The S shows an overall negative sign signifying the electron type charge carriers dominate in this compound. The negative S decreases with increase in Mn concentration.